

On Wiener and Weighted Wiener Indices of Neighborhood Corona of Two Graphs

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Abstract: In this paper, we compute the Wiener index, degree distance index and Gutman index of neighborhood corona of two graphs.

Key Words: Neighborhood corona, Wiener index, degree distance index, Gutman index.

AMS(2010): 05C12, 05C07, 05C76

§1. Introduction

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected simple graph. The distance between two vertices u and v in G , denoted by $d_G(u, v)$ is the length of a shortest path between u and v in G . The degree of a vertex u in G , denoted by $d_G(u)$ is the number of vertices that are adjacent to u in G . The Wiener index $W(G)$ of a graph G is a distance based graph invariant introduced by H. Wiener [18] in order to determine the boiling point of paraffin. It is defined as the sum of distance between all pairs of vertices in G . i.e., $W(G) = \sum_{\{u,v\} \subseteq V(G)} d_G(u, v)$. The degree distance index $DD(G)$ and Gutman index $Gut(G)$ of a graph are weighted versions of Wiener index, which are defined as follows:

$$DD(G) = \sum_{\{u,v\} \subseteq V(G)} (d_G(u) + d_G(v))d_G(u, v)$$

and

$$Gut(G) = \sum_{\{u,v\} \subseteq V(G)} d_G(u) d_G(v) d_G(u, v).$$

The degree distance index which is a degree distance based graph invariant, was introduced independently by A. A. Dobrynin, A. A. Kochetova [6] and I. Gutman [10]. The Gutman index, earlier known as Schultz index of the second kind was introduced in 1994 by Gutman [10]. It may be noted that if G is a tree on n vertices, then the Wiener index, degree distance index and Gutman index are closely related by the identities $DD(G) = 4W(G) - n(n - 1)$ and

¹Received December 9, 2015, Accepted November 15, 2016.

$Gut(G) = 4W(G) - (2n - 1)(n - 1)$. More details about Wiener index and its variants can be found in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 12, 14, 17] and the references cited therein.

The corona [9] of two graphs G_1 and G_2 is the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 , $|V(G_1)|$ copies of G_2 and joining each i -th vertex of G_1 to every vertex in the i -th copy of G_2 . The neighborhood corona [13] of two graphs G_1 and G_2 denoted by $G_1 * G_2$, is a variant of corona of two graphs and is defined as the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 and $|V(G_1)|$ copies of G_2 , and joining every neighbour of the i -th vertex of G_1 to every vertex in the i -th copy of G_2 . Recently, various graph invariants of corona product of two graphs have been studied, for example, see [1, 15, 19].

Example 1.1 The neighborhood corona $P_3 * P_2$.

Fig. 1. $P_3 * P_2$.

In this paper, we compute Wiener index, degree distance index and Gutman index of $G_1 * G_2$.

§2. Main Results

Let G_1 be a graph with vertex set $V(G_1) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_1}\}$, edge $E(G_1) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{m_1}\}$ and let G_2 be a graph with vertex set $V(G_2) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n_2}\}$ and edge set $E(G_2) = \{e'_1, e'_2, \dots, e'_{m_2}\}$. We denote the vertex set of the i -th copy of G_2 by $V_i(G_2) = \{u_{i1}, u_{i2}, \dots, u_{in_2}\}$.

To prove our main results we need the following definitions and two lemmas whose proofs follows directly by the definition of neighborhood corona.

Definition 2.1 For a graph G , we define

$$E_{\Delta}(G) := \{e \in E(G) : e \text{ is contained in a triangle of } G\},$$

$$T_1(G) := \sum_{uv \in E_{\Delta}(G)} d(u) + d(v) \text{ and } T_2(G) := \sum_{uv \in E_{\Delta}(G)} d(u)d(v).$$

Clearly, if G has a vertex v of degree of $|V(G)| - 1$ and $G - v$ is connected graph with at least two vertices, then $E_{\Delta}(G) = E(G)$, $T_1(G) = M_1(G)$ and $T_2(G) = M_2(G)$.

Lemma 2.2 Let $G = G_1 * G_2$. Then

$$d_G(x) = \begin{cases} (n_2 + 1)d_{G_1}(x), & \text{if } x \in V(G_1), \\ d_{G_2}(x) + d_{G_1}(v_i), & \text{if } x \in V_i(G_2). \end{cases}$$

Lemma 2.3 If $G = G_1 * G_2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \quad & d_G(v_i, v_j) = d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j), \forall v_i, v_j \in V(G_1); \\ (2) \quad & d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } u_j u_k \in E(G_2), \\ 2, & \text{if } u_j u_k \notin E(G_2). \end{cases} ; \\ (3) \quad & \text{for } i \neq k, d_G(u_{ij}, u_{km}) = \begin{cases} 3, & \text{if } v_i v_k \in E(G_1) \text{ and } v_i v_k \notin E_{\Delta}(G_1), \\ 2, & \text{if } v_i v_k \in E_{\Delta}(G_1), \\ d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k), & \text{if } v_i v_k \notin E(G_1). \end{cases} ; \\ (4) \quad & d_G(u_{ij}, v_k) = \begin{cases} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k), & \text{if } v_i \neq v_k, \\ 2, & \text{if } v_i = v_k. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.4 The Wiener index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by

$$W(G) = (n_2 + 1)^2 W(G_1) + n_1(n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2) + n_2^2(2m_1 - |E_{\Delta}(G_1)|) + 2n_1n_2.$$

Proof We know that

$$W(G) = \sum_{\{x, y\} \subseteq V(G)} d_G(x, y) = A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + A_4, \tag{2.1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_G(v_i, v_j), \\ A_2 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}), \\ A_3 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}, u_{jm}) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$A_4 = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1)}} d_G(u_{ij}, v_k).$$

By Lemma 2.3, we have

$$A_1 = \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_G(v_i, v_j) = \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) = W(G_1), \quad (2.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}) \\ &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} 2 - \sum_{u_j, u_k \in E(G_2)} 1 \right\} \\ &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} (n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2) = n_1(n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2), \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_3 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}, u_{jm}) \\ &= n_2^2 \left\{ \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) + \sum_{v_i, v_j \in E(G_1)} 2 - \sum_{v_i, v_j \in E_\Delta(G_1)} 1 \right\} \\ &= n_2^2(W(G_1) + 2m_1 - |E_\Delta(G_1)|) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} A_4 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1) \\ v_k \neq v_i}} d_G(v_k, u_{ij}) + \sum_{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2)} 2 \right\} \\ &= n_2 \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{v_k \in V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k) + 2n_1n_2 \\ &= 2n_2W(G_1) + 2n_1n_2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Applying (2.2), (2.3), (2.4) and (2.5) in (2.1), we obtain the desired result. \square

Corollary 2.5 *If G_1 is a triangle free graph, then the Wiener index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$W(G) = (n_2 + 1)^2 W(G_1) + n_1(n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2) + 2n_2^2 m_1 + 2n_1 n_2.$$

Corollary 2.6 *If $G_1 = H_1 \vee H_2$ (join of two connected graphs H_1 and H_2 with $|V(H_1)| \geq 2$), then the Wiener index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$W(G) = (n_2 + 1)^2 W(G_1) + n_1(n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2) + n_2^2 m_1 + 2n_1 n_2.$$

Lemma 2.7([4]) *Let P_n and C_n denote the path and cycle on n vertices, respectively. Then*

$$W(P_n) = \frac{n(n^2 - 1)}{6}$$

and

$$W(C_n) = \begin{cases} n^3/8, & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ n(n^2 - 1)/8, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Applying the above lemma in Theorem 2.4, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 2.8 (1) $W(P_n * P_m) = \frac{1}{6}((m + 1)^2 n^3 + (17m^2 - 2m + 5)n) - 2m^2$;
 (2) $W(C_{2n} * C_m) = ((m + 1)^2 n^2 + 6m^2)n$;
 (3) For $n \neq 1$, $W(C_{2n+1} * C_m) = (2n + 1)(m^2 n^2 + m^2 n + 2mn^2 + 6m^2 + 2mn + n^2 + n)/2$;
 (4) For $n \neq 1$, $W(C_{2n+1} * P_m) = (2n + 1)(m^2 n^2 + m^2 n + 2mn^2 + 6m^2 + 2mn + n^2 + n + 2)/2$;
 (5) $W(C_{2n} * P_m) = m^2 n^3 + 2mn^3 + 6m^2 n + n^3 + 2n$;
 (6) $W(P_n * C_m) = \frac{1}{6}((m + 1)^2 n^3 + (17m^2 - 2m - 1)n) - 2m^2$.

The first and second Zagreb indices of a graph denoted by $M_1(G)$ and $M_2(G)$, respectively, are degree based topological indices introduced by Gutman and N. Trinajstić ([11]). These two indices are defined as

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{e_i=v_l v_m \in E(G)} d_G(v_l) + d_G(v_m) = \sum_{v_i \in G} d_G^2(v_i)$$

and

$$M_2(G) = \sum_{e_i=v_l v_m \in E(G)} d_G(v_l) d_G(v_m).$$

Now, we derive a formula for $DD(G_1 * G_2)$ in terms of degree distance of G_1 , Wiener index of G_1 and first Zagreb index of G_1 and G_2 .

Theorem 2.9 *The degree distance index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$DD(G) = (2n_2^2 + 3n_2 + 1)DD(G_1) + 4m_2(n_2 + 1)W(G_1) + n_2^2(2M_1(G_1) - T_1(G_1)) \\ - n_1M_1(G_2) + (8n_2^2 + (8m_2 + 4)n_2 - 4m_2)m_1 + 4m_2n_2(n_1 - |E_\Delta(G_1)|).$$

Proof We know that

$$DD(G) = \sum_{\{x,y\} \subseteq V(G)} (d_G(x) + d_G(y)) d_G(x, y) = A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + A_4, \quad (2.6)$$

where

$$A_1 = \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} (d_G(v_i) + d_G(v_j)) d_G(v_i, v_j), \\ A_2 = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} [d_G(u_{ij}) + d_G(u_{ik})] d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}), \\ A_3 = \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_G(u_{ik}) + d_G(u_{jm})] d_G(u_{ik}, u_{jm})$$

and
$$A_4 = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1)}} [d_G(u_{ij}) + d_G(v_k)] d_G(u_{ij}, v_k).$$

Applying Lemmas 2.2 and 2.3, we compute A_1, A_2, A_3 and A_4 as follows:

$$A_1 = \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} (d_G(v_i) + d_G(v_j)) d_G(v_i, v_j) \\ = (n_2 + 1) \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} (d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) \\ = (n_2 + 1)DD(G_1). \quad (2.7)$$

$$A_2 = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} [d_G(u_{ij}) + d_G(u_{ik})] d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}) \\ = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ 2 \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} [2d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_2}(u_j) + d_{G_2}(u_k)] \right. \\ \left. - \sum_{u_j u_k \in E(G_2)} [2d_G(v_i) + d_{G_2}(u_j) + d_{G_2}(u_k)] \right\} \\ = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \{2(n_2(n_2 - 1)d_{G_1}(v_i) + 2(n_2 - 1)m_2) - 2m_2d_G(v_i) - M_1(G_2)\} \\ = 4(n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2)m_1 + 4n_1m_2(n_2 - 1) - n_1M_1(G_2). \quad (2.8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_3 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_G(u_{ik}) + d_G(u_{jm})] d_G(u_{ik}, u_{jm}) \\
 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j) + d_{G_2}(u_{ik}) + d_{G_2}(u_{jm})] \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j) + d_{G_2}(u_{ik}) + d_{G_2}(u_{jm})] \\
 &- \sum_{v_i v_j \in E_\Delta(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j) + d_{G_2}(u_{ik}) + d_{G_2}(u_{jm})] \\
 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) [n_2^2(d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) + 4n_2m_2] \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E(G_1)} [n_2^2(d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) + 4n_2m_2] \\
 &- \sum_{v_i v_j \in E_\Delta(G_1)} [n_2^2(d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) + 4n_2m_2] \\
 &= n_2^2 DD(G_1) + 4n_2m_2 W(G_1) + n_2^2(2M_1(G_1) - T_1(G_1)) + 4n_2m_2(2m_1 - |E_\Delta(G_1)|). \tag{2.9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_4 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1)}} [d_G(u_{ij}) + d_G(v_k)] d_G(u_{ij}, v_k) \\
 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1) \\ v_i \neq v_k}} [d_G(u_{ij}) + d_G(v_k)] d_G(u_{ij}, v_k) + 2 \sum_{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2)} (d_G(u_{ij}) + d_G(v_i)) \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ \sum_{v_k \in V(G_1)} (n_2 d_{G_1}(v_i) + n_2(n_2 + 1) d_{G_1}(v_k) + 2m_2) d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k) + 2[2m_2 + n_2(n_2 + 2)] d_G(v_i) \right\} \\
 &= (n_2^2 + 2n_2) DD(G_1) + 4m_2 W(G_1) + 4n_1 m_2 + 4m_1(n_2 + 2)n_2. \tag{2.10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Applying (2.7), (2.8), (2.9) and (2.10) in (2.6), we obtain the desired result. □

Corollary 2.10 *If G_1 is a triangle free graph, then the degree distance index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 DD(G) &= (2n_2^2 + 3n_2 + 1)DD(G_1) + 4m_2(n_2 + 1)W(G_1) + 2n_2^2M_1(G_1) \\
 &- n_1M_1(G_2) + (8n_2^2 + (8m_2 + 4)n_2 - 4m_2)m_1 + 4m_2n_2n_1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.11 *If $G_1 = H_1 \vee H_2$ (join of two connected graphs H_1 and H_2 with $|V(H_1)| \geq 2$),*

then the degree distance index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by

$$DD(G) = (2n_2^2 + 3n_2 + 1)DD(G_1) + 4m_2(n_2 + 1)W(G_1) + n_2^2M_1(G_1) \\ - n_1M_1(G_2) + (2n_2^2 + (m_2 + 1)n_2 - m_2)4m_1 + 4m_2n_2n_1.$$

Lemma 2.12([7,16]) *Let P_n and C_n denote the path and cycle on n vertices, respectively. Then*

$$DD(P_n) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n-1)}{3}$$

and

$$DD(C_n) = \begin{cases} n^3/2, & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ n(n^2-1)/2, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Using Lemmas 2.7, 2.12 and also the facts that $M_1(P_n) = 4n - 6$ ($n \geq 2$), $M_2(P_n) = 4n - 8$ ($n \geq 3$), $M_1(C_n) = M_2(C_n) = 4n$ in Theorem 2.9, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 2.13 (1) $DD(P_n * P_m) = (2n^3 - 2n^2 + 28n - 28)m^2 + (2n^3 - 3n^2 - 15n + 8)m - n^2 + 11n - 4$;

$$(2) DD(C_{2n} * C_m) = 4n(3m^2n^2 + 4mn^2 + 14m^2 + n^2 - 2m);$$

(3) for $n \neq 1$, $DD(C_{2n+1} * C_m) = 2(2n+1)(3m^2n^2 + 3m^2n + 4mn^2 + 14m^2 + 4mn + n^2 - 2m + n)$;

$$(4) \text{ for } n \neq 1, DD(C_{2n+1} * P_m) = 2(2n+1)(3m^2n^2 + 3m^2n + 3mn^2 + 14m^2 + 3mn - 8m + 5);$$

$$(5) DD(C_{2n} * P_m) = 4n(3m^2n^2 + 3mn^2 + 14m^2 - 8m + 5);$$

$$(6) DD(P_n * C_m) = \frac{1}{3}((6m^2 + 8m + 2)n^3 - (6m^2 + 9m + 3)n^2 + (84m^2 - 11m + 1)n) - 28m^2.$$

Now, we derive a formula for $Gut(G_1 * G_2)$ in terms of degree distance of G_1 , Gutman index of G_1 , Wiener index of G_1 and Zagreb indices of G_1 and G_2 .

Theorem 2.14 *The Gutman index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$Gut(G) = (2n_2 + 1)^2Gut(G_1) + 2m_2(2n_2 + 1)DD(G_1) + 4m_2^2W(G_1) - (n_1 + 2m_1)M_1(G_2) \\ - n_1M_2(G_2) + (n_2(3n_2 + 4m_2 + 1) - m_2)M_1(G_1) + n_2^2(2M_2(G_1) - T_2(G_1)) \\ - 2n_2m_2T_1(G_1) - 4m_2^2|E_{\Delta}(G_1)| + 8m_1m_2[2n_2 + m_2] + 4n_1m_2^2.$$

Proof Notice that

$$Gut(G) = \sum_{\{x,y\} \subseteq V(G)} (d_G(x) d_G(y)) d_G(x, y) = A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + A_4, \quad (2.11)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_G(v_i) d_G(v_j) d_G(v_i, v_j), \\
 A_2 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}), \\
 A_3 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{jm}) d_G(u_{ik}, u_{jm})
 \end{aligned}$$

and
$$A_4 = \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \frac{dv}{dx} \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1)}} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(v_k) d_G(u_{ij}, v_k).$$

Applying Lemmas 2.2 and 2.3, $A_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ can be computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_G(v_i) d_G(v_j) d_G(v_i, v_j) \\
 &= (n_2 + 1)^2 \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} [d_{G_1}(v_i) d_{G_1}(v_j)] d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) = (n_2 + 1)^2 Gut(G_1), \tag{2.12}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_2 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{ij}, u_{ik}) \\
 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ 2 \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(u_{ik}) - \sum_{u_j u_k \in E(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(u_{ik}) \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ 2 \sum_{\{u_{ij}, u_{ik}\} \subseteq V_i(G_2)} [d_{G_2}(u_{ij}) d_{G_2}(u_{ik}) + d_{G_1}(v_i) (d_{G_2}(u_{ij}) + d_{G_2}(u_{ik})) + d_G^2(v_i)] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \sum_{u_j u_k \in E(G_2)} (d_{G_2}(u_{ij}) d_{G_2}(u_{ik}) + d_{G_1}(v_i) [d_{G_2}(u_{ij}) + d_{G_2}(u_{ik})] + d_G^2(v_i)) \right\} \\
 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ 4m_2^2 - M_1(G_2) + 4(n_2 - 1)m_2 d_{G_1}(v_i) + n_2(n_2 - 1)d_G^2(v_i) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - M_2(G_2) - d_G(v_i)M_1(G_2) - m_2 d_G^2(v_i) \right\} \\
 &= n_1(4m_2^2 - M_2(G_2)) - (n_1 + 2m_1)M_1(G_2) + 8m_1 m_2(n_2 - 1) + (n_2(n_2 - 1) - m_2)M_1(G_1), \tag{2.13}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_3 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{jm}) d_G(u_{ik}, u_{jm}) \\
 &= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{jm}) d_{G_1}(v_i, v_j) \\
 &\quad + 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{jm}) - \sum_{v_i v_j \in E_\Delta(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} d_G(u_{ik}) d_G(u_{jm})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k) \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_2}(u_k)] [d_{G_1}(v_j) + d_{G_2}(u_m)] \\
&+ 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_2}(u_k)] [d_{G_1}(v_j) + d_{G_2}(u_m)] \\
&- \sum_{v_i v_j \in E_\Delta(G_1)} \sum_{\substack{u_{ik} \in V_i(G_2) \\ u_{jm} \in V_j(G_2)}} [d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_2}(u_k)] [d_{G_1}(v_j) + d_{G_2}(u_m)] \\
&= \sum_{\{v_i, v_j\} \subseteq V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k) \left\{ n_2^2 d_{G_1}(v_i) d_{G_1}(v_j) + 2n_2 m_2 (d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) + 4m_2^2 \right\} \\
&+ 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E(G_1)} \left\{ n_2^2 d_{G_1}(v_i) d_{G_1}(v_j) + 2n_2 m_2 (d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) + 4m_2^2 \right\} \\
&- \sum_{v_i v_j \in E_\Delta(G_1)} \left\{ n_2^2 d_{G_1}(v_i) d_{G_1}(v_j) + 2n_2 m_2 (d_{G_1}(v_i) + d_{G_1}(v_j)) + 4m_2^2 \right\} \\
&= n_2^2 \text{Gut}(G_1) + 2n_2 m_2 \text{DD}(G_1) + 4m_2^2 \text{W}(G_1) + n_2^2 (2M_2(G_1) - T_2(G_1)) \\
&+ 2n_2 m_2 (2M_1(G_1) - T_1(G_1)) + 4m_2^2 (2m_1 - |E_\Delta(G_1)|). \tag{2.14}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_4 &= \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2) \\ v_k \in V(G_1) \\ v_i \neq v_k}} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(v_k) d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k) + 2 \sum_{u_{ij} \in V_i(G_2)} d_G(u_{ij}) d_G(v_i) \right\} \\
&= (n_2 + 1) \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} \left\{ \sum_{v_k \in V(G_1)} d_{G_1}(v_i, v_k) d_{G_1}(v_k) (2m_2 + n_2 d_{G_1}(v_i)) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2 (n_2 d_{G_1}^2(v_i) + 2m_2 d_{G_1}(v_i)) \right\} \\
&= 2(n_2 + 1)(m_2 \text{DD}(G_1) + n_2 \text{Gut}(G_1) + n_2 M_1(G_1) + 4m_1 m_2). \tag{2.15}
\end{aligned}$$

Using (2.12), (2.13), (2.14) and (2.15) in (2.11), we obtain the required result. \square

Corollary 2.15 *If G_1 is a triangle free graph, then the Gutman index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Gut}(G) &= (2n_2 + 1)^2 \text{Gut}(G_1) + 2m_2(2n_2 + 1) \text{DD}(G_1) + 4m_2^2 \text{W}(G_1) \\
&\quad - (n_1 + 2m_1) M_1(G_2) - n_1 M_2(G_2) + (n_2(3n_2 + 4m_2 + 1) - m_2) M_1(G_1) \\
&\quad + 2n_2^2 M_2(G_1) + 8m_1 m_2 [2n_2 + m_2] + 4n_1 m_2^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.16 *If $G_1 = H_1 \vee H_2$ (join of two connected graphs H_1 and H_2 with $|V(H_1)| \geq 2$), then the Gutman index of $G = G_1 * G_2$ is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} Gut(G) &= (2n_2 + 1)^2 Gut(G_1) + 2m_2(2n_2 + 1)DD(G_1) + 4m_2^2W(G_1) \\ &\quad - (n_1 + 2m_1)M_1(G_2) - n_1M_2(G_2) + (n_2(3n_2 + 2m_2 + 1) - m_2)M_1(G_1) \\ &\quad + n_2^2M_2(G_1) + 4m_1m_2[4n_2 + m_2] + 4n_1m_2^2. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.17([8]) *Let P_n and C_n denote the path and the cycle on n vertices, respectively. Then*

$$Gut(P_n) = (n - 1)(2n^2 - 4n + 3)/3$$

and

$$Gut(C_n) = \begin{cases} n^3/2, & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ n(n^2 - 1)/2, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Applying Lemmas 2.7, 2.12 and 2.17 in Theorem 2.14, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 2.18 (1) *For $n, m \geq 3$, $Gut(P_n * P_m) = (6n^3 - 12n^2 + 74n - 86)m^2 - (6n^2 + 62n - 60)m + 43n - 27$;*

$$(2) \quad Gut(C_{2n} * C_m) = 4n(9m^2n^2 + 6mn^2 + 32m^2 + n^2 - 8m);$$

(3) *For $n \neq 1$, $Gut(C_{2n+1} * C_m) = 2(2n + 1)(9m^2n^2 + 9m^2n + 6mn^2 + 32m^2 + 6mn + n^2 - 8m + n)$;*

$$(4) \quad \text{For } n \neq 1, \quad Gut(C_{2n+1} * P_m) = 2(2n + 1)(9m^2n^2 + 9m^2n + 32m^2 - 36m + 21);$$

$$(5) \quad Gut(C_{2n} * P_m) = 4n(9m^2n^2 + 32m^2 - 36m + 21);$$

(6) $Gut(P_n * C_m) = 6(m + 1/3)^2n^3 - \frac{1}{3}((36m^2 + 30m + 6)n^2 + (222m^2 - 18m + 7)n) - 86m^2 + 4m - 1$.

Acknowledgement

The second author is thankful to UGC, New Delhi, for UGC-JRF, under which this work has been done.

References

- [1] C. Adiga, Malpashree R, Rakshith B. R, N. Anitha, Some topological indices of edge corona of two graphs, *Iranian J. Math. Chem.*, accepted.
- [2] V. Andova, D. Dimitrov, J. Fink, R. Škrekovski, Bounds on Gutman index, *MATCH Commun. Math. Comput. Chem.*, 67 (2012) 515–524.
- [3] P. Dankelmann, I. Gutman, S. Mukwembi, H.C. Swart, On the degree distance of a graph, *Discrete Appl. Math.*, 157 (2009) 2773–2777.

- [4] A. A. Dobrynin, R. Entringer, I. Gutman, Wiener index of trees: theory and applications, *Acta Appl. Math.*, 66 (2001) 211–249.
- [5] A. A. Dobrynin, I. Gutman, S. Klavžar, P. Žigert, Wiener index of hexagonal systems, *Acta Appl. Math.*, 72 (2002) 247–294.
- [6] A. A. Dobrynin, A. A. Kochetova, Degree distance of a graph: a degree analogue of the Wiener index, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 34 (1994) 1082–1086.
- [7] M. Essalih, M. E. Marraki and G. E. Hagri, Calculation of Some Topological Indices of Graphs, *J. Theor. Appl. Inf. Tech.*, 30 (2011) 122–127.
- [8] L. Feng and W. Liu, The maximal Gutman index of bicyclic graphs, *MATCH Commun. Math. Comput. Chem.*, 66 (2011) 699–708.
- [9] R. Frucht, F. Harary, On the corona of two graphs, *Aequationes Math.*, 4 (1970) 322–325.
- [10] I. Gutman, Selected properties of Schultz molecular topological index, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 34 (1994) 1087–1089.
- [11] I. Gutman, N. Trinajstić, Graph theory and molecular orbitals, total π electron energy of alternant hydrocarbons, *Chemical Physics Letters*, 17 (1972) 535–538.
- [12] I. Gutman, S. Klavžar, B. Mohar (eds.), Fifty years of the Wiener index, *MATCH Commun. Math. Comput. Chem.*, 35 (1997) 1–259.
- [13] G. Indulal, The spectrum of neighborhood corona of graphs, *Kragujevac J. Math.*, 35 (2011) 493–500.
- [14] M. Knor, P. Potočnik, R. Škrekovski, Relationship between the edge-Wiener index and the Gutman index of a graph, *Discrete Appl. Math.*, 167 (2014) 197–201.
- [15] V. Sheeba Agnes, Degree distance and Gutman index of corona product of graphs, *Trans. Combin.*, 4 (2015) 11–23.
- [16] I. Tomescu, Some extremal properties of the degree distance of a graph, *Discrete Appl. Math.*, 98 (1999) 159–163.
- [17] A. I. Tomescu, Unicyclic and bicyclic graphs having minimum degree distance, *Discrete Appl. Math.*, 156 (2008) 125–130.
- [18] H. Wiener, Structural determination of paraffin boiling points, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 69 (1947) 17–20.
- [19] Z. Yarahmadi, A. R. Ashrafi, The Szeged, vertex PI, first and second Zagreb indices of corona product of graphs, *Filomat*, 26:3 (2012) 467–472.